

Analyzing the Freedom of Information Requests Using Topic Modeling: Towards User-driven Open Government Data Ecosystems

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Abstract

Open data has become an important player in promoting government transparency and accountability around the globe. Governments have established policies to provide citizens or users with access to data. One way to obtain such data is through Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) requests. Considering users' requests for data and responding with the required information makes open data ecosystems user-driven. This paper explores freedom of information (FOI) requests received by Germany's Ministry of Health as a user-driven approach to open government data (OGD). By applying advanced natural language processing (NLP) techniques, specifically Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and BERTopic, we analyze a large corpus of FOI requests to identify key topics and trends in public inquiries. The findings reveal valuable insights into citizens' information demands and demonstrate the strengths of these NLP methods in extracting actionable patterns. In this way, governments can easily understand user needs in health-related datasets (this study, in particular, focuses on requests made by citizens related to COVID-19 data). This study lays the groundwork in two ways: first, by understanding and thematically categorizing user needs related to open data, and second, by improving government data transparency, informing the prioritization of dataset releases, and supporting evidence-based policymaking.

CCS Concepts

• Insert your first CCS term here; • Insert your second CCS term here; • Insert your third CCS term here;

Keywords

Freedom of Information, Open Government Data, Open Data, Open Data Ecosystems, Topic Modeling

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1 INTRODUCTION

There has been a strong push for more transparent governments in recent years. Initiatives like the Open Government Partnership drive toward more transparency, digitalized administration, and citizen engagement. Government information should be available as open data, allowing citizens to engage further in administrative procedures and policymaking [19, 20]. While there are arguments that all government data should be published in real-time and made available to the public [ibid], there are also claims about prioritizing data publication [8, 20, 24]. In addition, there are arguments over what kind of datasets governments should compile to meet citizens' information needs. Yet, governments need to know what datasets citizens are interested in to do so. Public health concerns every citizen. From questions around treatment evaluation and costs to policy and planning, political decisions implicate people's everyday lives. However, determining what type of health datasets should be published is challenging, with the versatile data landscape this field offers, and the challenges in data preparation on the one side and citizens' needs on the other side. Governments and administrations need to tap into the rich information potential of what data citizens would like to see published. In this line, the concept of user-driven open data governments comes into action.

The transition to user-driven open government data (OGD) is gathering momentum. Loenen (2018) suggests a five-step methodology for data suppliers to develop user-oriented policies, underscoring the significance of involving users in decision-making [26]. To facilitate this transition, Luthfi and Janssen (2022) created a reference architecture for OGD portals that emphasizes user empowerment through improved functionalities [13]. Younsi Dahbi et al. (2019) propose a method to enhance the discoverability of data on OGD portals by suggesting pertinent datasets customized to users' interests [5]. Crusoe and Ahlin (2019) offer a comprehensive user process framework that delineates the activities and variations in OGD usage, thereby providing valuable insights for users, publishers, and portal proprietors [4]. These studies demonstrate the necessity of a user-centered approach in OGD initiatives, underscoring the significance of comprehending user requirements, enhancing data accessibility, and enabling the development of new digital products and services. This study proposes a framework that will exploit the user requests to receive specific information,

exemplified by health data, to make the open data more user-driven and respond to the users' needs more appropriately and efficiently by opening data they are interested in. Under the Freedom of Information (FOI) Act, governments advocating for open governance receive and then collect requests for information from their citizens. Using those user requests and appropriate responses to the requests for information contributes to user-driven open data ecosystems.

While there is some research on using FOI to receive information for research [3, 15, 23], there is limited research using FOI requests to determine citizen's interest in a topic [22]. Hence, there is not much groundwork laid out for analyzing FOI requests. This research uses two Natural Language Processing techniques, namely BERTopic and LDA, to answer the following research questions:

1. Do FOI requests provide information for the user-driven open data ecosystem?

- a) What are the obstacles in data collection and analysis?
- b) How can we automate the identification of Users' interests in open data by analyzing the requests received from the open data publishers (ministries)?

The literature review will give an overview of the current state of research by looking at citizen participation, usability, and feedback loops and showing gaps in analyzing user interests. It will highlight the benefits of open data and the background of data publication prioritization exemplified by the European Commission's approach to defining high-value datasets. Freedom of information and its concept will be highlighted to analyze user needs. Then, the proposed methodology is explained by looking at quantitative content analysis in general and specifically at the two methods used for this research - LDA and BERTopic. The practical application example will explain those two concepts in the analysis section. Further on, the outcomes of the methodologies in the form of results and analysis are described in detail, and the two methods (BERTopic and LDA) are contrasted. Finally, the outcomes are discussed, the research is put into the context of the research questions, and an outlook of further possible research that the authors of this paper recommend is given.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review shows gaps in the research on what government information citizens want to see published. For example, while there is research on citizen participation and the creation of feedback loops for citizens [6] and analysis on the usability of already published data [12, 14], it is vague when trying to specify how citizens' interests can influence the prioritization of the publication of datasets. While government entities might be hesitant to publish datasets because they fear what can be done with the dataset [31], there is a push to open data by default and create a new norm of openness [29]. To this end, Noveck 2017 emphasizes that the open data narrative states that the government should be open since the taxpayer pays for the data collection. In addition to the ideas behind open data, the benefit ranges from business ideas [16, 27] to better government performance [1] and creating space for citizen participation [1, 20]. While open data researchers agree on the benefits of open data for citizens, the definition of data publication prioritization is complex.

Defining high-value datasets is one way to rank datasets to determine which publication is prioritized. These datasets should be re-usable with minimal legal restrictions and free of charge [18]. However, the definition of value is different for each stakeholder involved. In comparison, data owners create value by publishing to fulfill legal obligations, increase transparency, raise awareness on a specific topic, and reduce costs [28]. For re-users, the size of the target audience and the number of services or systems using the dataset indicate the value (ibid.). Following Zuiderwijk and Janssen (2014), open data is driven by transparency, increasing citizens' participation, and stimulating economic growth [30]. While those two definitions of the value of datasets do not necessarily oppose each other, they indicate a big span of interest that needs catering. To find out what data users are interested in, the European Commission conducted a user consultation as part of the exercise to define high-value datasets [8]. The European Commission released a list of high-value datasets to be published by governments within 18 months, putting pressure on progressing with opening datasets. For example, in terms of health, the statistics on current healthcare expenditures are on the list of datasets in scope [8].

While freedom of information is seen as a product of legal regulation and the backbone of citizen participation [Birkinshaw 2010], open government data is often referred to as a technical process, not a necessary response to legal frameworks [19, 20, 29, 31]. Zuiderwijk et al. (2014) even call FOI a "passive approach to releasing information), while one needs to bear in mind that freedom of information legally means the right to documentation and not information. In contrast to FOI, open data is the more active approach to informing citizens, posting data ex-ante, publishing datasets focusing on the workings of government, and addressing a broader audience [17]. Traditionally, FOI is used more by journalists, lawyers, charitable trusts, and applicants who submit multiple requests (Bundesbeauftragter für den Datenschutz und Informationsfreiheit 2018); open data is also used by the data publishers themselves and businesses [17].

When citizens feel the need to complement data that governments might not have available, they generate it, creating citizen-generated data [2, 11]. This data ranges from environmental information on air pollution to maps indicating harassment locations [2]. Sometimes, freedom of information requests is used strategically in campaigning, leading to data release. The published data is not generated by civil society or citizens, which does not directly make it citizen-generated. Still, it is only released due to citizen requests, which would make it citizen-demanded data or, as Loenen et al. (2021) [25] mention, the user-driven open data eco-systems in, e.g., geography, education, agriculture, finance, and law. In Germany, the civil society organization Open Knowledge Foundation operates an online portal enabling citizens to submit Freedom of Information (FOI) requests. Through this platform, users can direct their requests to specific government entities. Once the information is provided, the request and the official response are published on the portal, making the data publicly accessible. The organization has also organized targeted campaigns to unlock important datasets. For example, it successfully campaigned for the release of internal research conducted by the German Bundestag and hygiene inspections conducted by local health authorities in restaurants. As a direct outcome of these efforts, the German Parliament (in German,

Figure 1: Proposed methodology for analyzing the Freedom of Information requests using topic modeling algorithms

it’s called Bundestag¹) has since begun publishing its research as open data, marking a significant step toward greater government transparency and public access to information.

For this research, computer-assisted methods are used and tested, with a sample size of n=1320. Automated methodologies will also be advantageous for replicating and updating the analysis with new data. For this analysis, topic modeling and, more specifically, the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), a model that assumes that each document contains a mixture of different topics [10, 22]. In the last couple of years, new topic modeling systems using embedded systems have been added to the landscape of tools used in NLP [7]. In addition to LDA, the authors have decided to use BERTopic to compare both topic modeling systems and their outcomes. In contrast to LDA, BERTopic discovers hidden semantic structures in a given document. In the examined dataset, the FOI requests are relatively short, which will challenge the performance of the proposed methods.

3 PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

To analyze the Freedom of Information (FOI) requests submitted to Germany’s Health Ministry, a comprehensive methodology shown in Figure 1 has been developed to uncover the key topics or themes users are most interested in. This approach aims to identify patterns in the types of data requested, shedding light on the areas where citizens seek greater transparency and access to open data.

- **Dataset:** The dataset was retrieved via a FOI request through the portal Frag den Staat. It covers 2020, 2021, and 2022 (up until April 2022).
- **Preprocessing:** The dataset was received in German in pdf format. It was then converted into xls and translated via Google Translate, and errors were corrected manually. After testing the entire dataset, the data on two campaigns was manually removed. For LDA, the list of unwanted stop words was applied. The selection of the stop words was done manually. Those were words that did not contribute to the topic modeling (“request”, “many”, “use”, “ask”, “etc”, “new”, “particular”, “according”, “regarding”, “available”, “ask”, “etc”, “new”, “particular”, “eg”, “e”, “v”). The preprocessing function employs regular expressions to eliminate punctuation, numerals, and links and subsequently converts all words to lowercase to guarantee consistency. Subsequently, the

text is tokenized into individual words, and the NLTK stop-words list is implemented to eliminate stop words (common words like “the” and “and”). This procedure creates a new “cleaned_corpus” column containing the processed text.

- **Topic Modeling:**
- **LDA:** A cleaned textual data frame is employed to implement the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic model. The documents are converted into a document-term matrix (DTM) using ‘CountVectorizer’, a sparse representation of the frequency of terms in the documents, also called conventional features. Each row of the DTM corresponds to a document, while each column represents a distinct term from the corpus. The values in the matrix represent the count of each term in the corresponding document, excluding common stop words and applying thresholds for document frequency to guarantee that only pertinent terms are included. This process entails establishing minimum and maximum thresholds to exclude overly common or rare terms. An LDA model is generated with a predetermined number of topics (five in this instance) and subsequently adapted to the DTM. The model subsequently extracts and presents the most prominent words associated with each topic, providing a deeper understanding of the topics in the corpus. This method effectively identifies and outlines the primary topics in the dataset.
- **BERTopic:** A data frame comprising textual data is employed to implement the Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) topic model, referred to as BERTopic. The textual data is extracted and transformed into a list of documents for analysis. The BERTopic model is instantiated with the parameter nr_topics set to nine (actually 8, but one topic is designated as -1, which contains irrelevant topics). This indicates that the model should identify eight discrete topics within the dataset. The fit_transform method is applied to the list of documents, generating BERT embeddings that capture the contextual relationships (or semantic relationships) between the words. Two outputs are generated by the method: the probabilities that indicate the degree to which each document relates to its assigned topic and the topic labels allocated to each document. These embeddings are clustered to form topics. This method effectively utilizes BERT embeddings to identify and outline the primary topics in the dataset.

¹<https://www.bundestag.de/en>

- Evaluation methods:** To determine the optimal number of topics for our topic modeling approach, we employed systematic methods for both Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and BERTopic, ensuring a data-driven and robust selection. For LDA, we conducted a Grid Search with 10-fold cross-validation to explore different configurations of the model. The evaluation was based on the log-likelihood scores, which reflect how well the model fits the data. After assessing the log-likelihood values and examining their trends across different topic numbers, we observed diminishing returns for larger topic counts. Consequently, we determined that five topics struck the best balance between model complexity and interpretability, resulting in an optimal choice for LDA. For BERTopic, we leveraged the intertopic distance map from the topic visualization tool. This map provides insights into the relationships and distances between topics, helping to avoid topic redundancy while ensuring coverage of distinct themes. Based on this visual analysis, we recognized that eight topics offered the most meaningful and well-separated topic clusters. Therefore, we selected eight topics as the optimal number for BERTopic, ensuring both cohesion within topics and sufficient differentiation between them. By applying these tailored methods, we identified the most suitable number of topics for both LDA and BERTopic, ensuring both models provide coherent and interpretable results.
- Analysis and results:** Synthesizing the topics into the taxonomy, explaining them regarding FOIA, and describing challenges of the topic modeling methods. The steps explained in the proposed methodology have helped the authors achieve results, which are presented in the next section in more detail.

4 ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 General Procedure and Preprocessing

The data gathered was requested via a freedom of information request via the portal *Frag den Staat* to the federal Ministry of Health in Germany. Since the data publication created additional work for the administration, a fee was charged for the data, which was first sent as a paper printout and later, as per the authors' request, as a PDF. The PDF was converted into a spreadsheet and then translated with Google Translate. The dataset sent to the authors included, in some cases, short sentences on the FOI request and sometimes lengthier text, which might be because the administration summarized some of the requests at the ministry before being sent to the authors. The translation was checked manually at random, and errors were corrected manually. A first check of the dataset showed a lot of repetition of the same wording in sentences of requests with different names of members of parliament. The authors found that this was due to two campaigns run by *Frag den Staat*, the 'Campaign Act of Honour'², which was responsible for 412 FOI (over 35% of the total) requests in this dataset, and the "Make your

²The 'Campaign Act of Honour' (in German: *Aktion Ehrensache*) <https://fragdenstaat.de/aktionen/ehrensache/> was a campaign which aimed to find out which politicians were involved in the procurement of corona masks. Within three hours all the contacts of the social and christ democrats were requested in order to shine a light on their involvement on mask deals.

own lobby registry³ " campaign, which included 135 FOI requests in the dataset. The analysis was then run once, including the requests made during the campaigns and then without the campaigns. The data sample size $n=1320$ without campaigns was then further analyzed to understand better what data citizens are interested in without any stimulation by campaigners.

A word cloud with the most prominent words (see Figure 2) is the first indicator of the main discussion topics. Some of the most mentioned words are just a reference or an indicator of the nature of the information requested, such as information, document, contract, correspondence, report, meeting, study, decision, or words that are usually used in this type of communication with authorities such as sending, e.g., question or request. Here, the most prominent words are BMG, health information, and document, due to the sample selected, which were only requests to the Ministry of Health and then corona, covid, and vaccination, which is a clear first indicator of citizens' interest in information/ documentation on COVID19.

4.2 Topic modeling using LDA and analysis

The first analysis was done after creating a word cloud of the most repetitive words in the corpus. Here, the researchers discovered a couple of typical FOI request texts. Some of the words could be described as typical FOI requests text such as information, document, file, overview, number, record, number, request, sending documents, regarding, available, statement, contact, data, question, communication, according, result, many, use, ask, etc, new, particular, eg, e, v. Highlighted are those stop words that did not add meaning to the clusters and were cleared from the dataset in a next step. The optimal number of clusters is crucial for further analysis. After removing any stop words, the authors used the elbow method to determine the ideal number of clusters. The elbow method indicated an optimal number of 3 or 5 clusters. While three is not distinct enough, with too many words merged and the topics too broad for further analysis, five clusters are more appropriate here. The average topic distribution for all five topics is 20%, which shows that the distribution across all documents is quite even for the five topics. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of topic distribution indicates that the topics are close to the average with only a couple of outliers (see Figure 3, PCA of topic distribution), which indicates a balanced topic distribution.

After the first round of clustering, it became evident that some numbers and punctuations were included in the cluster's top 20 most influential keywords. The authors then decided to remove those. This shifted the focus of the clusters and brought up some new focus in the FOI requests. While there was still a strong focus on COVID-19-related requests, the newly formed clusters focused more clearly on COVID-19 testing. In contrast, in the first round of analysis, the testing was mixed in other topics (see Table 1 LDA Clusters, including keywords and titles without numbers and punctuations). The second analysis also shows a more distinguished focus on topics unrelated to COVID-19, such as the healthcare system in general (ibid). Also, the topic of Cannabis was not even

³The Make your own lobby registry (in German: *Lobbyregister selbst gemacht*) <https://fragdenstaat.de/kampagnen/lobbyregister/> was a campaign aiming to make the meetings between MPs and lobbyists transparent.

Figure 2: word cloud of the most prominent words in LDA

Table 1: LDA Clusters including keywords and titles without numbers and punctuations

Topic number	Top 20 most influential keywords without numbers and punctuations	Topic Title
0	tests, sarscov, pcr, covid, bmg, test, number, spahn, federal, people, costs, cannabis, application, jens, infected, list, positive, quick, virus, communication	COVID-19 Testing and Pandemic Response Costs
1	corona, vaccination, documents, app, correspondence, vaccines, mask, information, test, protection, coronavirus, warn, costs, sending, bmg, germany, list, notes, masks, pandemic	COVID-19 Vaccination, App Usage, and Mask Regulations
2	bmg, vaccine, covid, sending, communication, house, open, management, level, rki, documents, contracts, delivery, vaccination, biontech, appointments, doses, information, internal, procedure	Vaccine Distribution and Government Communication
3	health, federal, information, ministry, documents, according, care, protection, vaccination, insurance, bmg, procurement, data, intensive, medical, hospitals, request, available, nursing, companies	Healthcare System and Vaccination Procurement
4	corona, status, report, contract, documents, vaccination, law, sending, vaccine, novavax, test, scientific, rki, numbers, epidemic, recovered, admission, risk, national, number	COVID-19 Reports, Vaccination Contracts, and Legal Framework

mentioned in the first analysis; the same applies to a clearer focus on administrative aspects such as contracts, procedures, and procurement (ibid.). This shows that citizens requested a lot of information that could have been published by the government directly. Especially legal information and statistics are areas where the information can easily be published as soon as it is available. Information on COVID-related purchases might be more complex due to the nature of the procurement process and the associated number of documents. In addition, the publication of those documents is associated with a far more complex process, which might involve further legislative changes before the publication. Still, there is

a clear indication that information and transparency concerning public contracting is an area of interest.

4.3 Topic Modeling using BERTopic and Analysis

A first analysis with BERTopic, including all data with campaigns (1867), returned 32 clusters. Here, the intertopical distance map showed that topics were . This could indicate that either the topics shared only little similarity, or the model was not the right fit, or that the topics were relatively sparse. Assuming that too many topics were returned (n=1320), an approach to reduce the topics

Figure 3: PCA of topic distribution

was needed. Here, the decision to leave out the campaigns was made, leading to a reduced size of topics (27) and an intertopical distance map with four clusters, indicating that the topics were close enough and could be narrowed down further. The number of topics that were COVID-19 related was 15 out of 27, which were summed up to 530 documents under the 15 clusters that included COVID-19-related topics. However, many topics were clustered under #-1 (358), defined under BERTopics as outliers or topics that cannot be categorized. Due to the high number of outliers, with 27.12% of the whole sample, the authors decided to test whether fewer topics would reduce the outliers. Here, the authors tested grouping the topics into eight clusters. Notably, the topic structure changed with the change of clusters modeled by BERTopic, so a direct comparison between the 27 clusters or eight clusters is not possible. The clustered eight topics returned a cluster of topic #-1, which was reduced to 304 documents, reducing the share to 23.03% of the whole sample. To keep the topics distinct, the authors decided to keep the eight topics and not reduce them further. The representation of words and proposed names by BERTopic showed three COVID-related clusters (topic #1, topic #5, and topic #6); on

investigating the representative documents, the authors discovered that three additional topics (topic #-1, topic #2 and topic #7) also included COVID-19 related documents (see Table 2 BERTopic clusters including count, representation, and title). All the documents in those clusters amount to 1255, bearing in mind that topic-1 includes outliers of the topics.

The authors renamed all topics, which helped better understand the topics citizens would be most interested in (Table 2 BERTopic clusters including count, representation, and title). The main interest after analyzing the dataset with BERTopic becomes clear. COVID-related information, especially that on vaccination, was requested by citizens. The intertopic distance map shows two main groups of clusters that are close to each other (while not overlapping) (see Figure 4 Inter-topic Distance Map and topic sizes using BERTopic Visualization feature). Those are topics #1, #2, #4, #6, #7, and topics #0, #3, and #5; the proximity indicates that the topics are more similar but distinct enough according to their distance on the map. The size of the circles around the topics indicates the

Table 2: BERTopic clusters including count, representation, and title

Topic	Count	Representations	Topic Title
-1	304	['the', 'of', 'to', 'in', 'and', 'for', 'on', 'with', 'from', 'bmg']	Miscellaneous or Unclassified Themes
0	499	['the', 'of', 'corona', 'vaccination', 'for', 'covid19', 'and', 'vaccine', 'in', 'to']	COVID-19 Vaccination
1	404	['the', 'of', 'and', 'to', 'in', 'bmg', 'on', 'for', 'health', 'with']	General Topics
2	31	['intensive', 'care', 'beds', 'emergency', 'in', 'bed', 'germany', 'hospitals', 'to', 'of']	Emergency Healthcare Capacity
3	21	['cannabis', 'legalization', 'of', 'tobacco', 'list', 'with', 'many', 'in', 'how', 'people']	Cannabis Legalization and Tobacco legislation
4	17	['status', 'recovered', 'omikron', 'shortening', 'recovery', 'validity', 'reduction', 'months', 'the', 'study']	Recovery Status and Omicron Variant
5	17	['pcr', 'tests', 'test', 'not', 'infected', 'is', 'tested', 'areas', 'positive', 'and']	PCR Testing
6	14	['advertising', 'expenditures', 'for', 'media', 'commercials', 'combat', 'especially', 'cost', 'campaign', 'covid19']	Media Advertising Expenditures
7	13	['data', 'protection', 'assessment', 'sequence', 'for', 'consequences', 'law', 'use', 'application', 'medical']	Data Protection and Assessment Protocols

Figure 4: Inter-topic Distance Map and topic sizes using BERTopic Visualization feature

topic’s prevalence in the text, which corresponds with the document count in the clusters (Table 2 BERTopic clusters including count, representation, and title).

4.4 Comparison between the topics identified by LDA and BERTopic

Both LDA and BERTopic return different clusters with some topics overlapping (see Figure 5 Distinct and common topics identified by LDA and BERTopic). It becomes evident that in both analyses, the

topic of COVID-19 is most prominent. However, the results and the topics of the two methodologies got closer after the last cleaning process in LDA. It became evident that the most notable common topic across both analyses was vaccination, which is reflected in multiple clusters (Figure 5 Distinct and common topics identified by LDA and BERTopic).

Citizens’ interests then were more specific with COVID-19 testing and the non-covid-related topic of healthcare capacity. Another topic that appeared in both analyses was the one on data protection and digital tools. The topics that are prominent in both analyses are a clear indication of what data citizens want to see published. Regarding vaccination and COVID-19 testing, this could be *information* such as vaccination roll-out or distribution, *statistics* on vaccinated people, or *legal information*. This information should be available to the administration without further data processing. Regarding healthcare capacity, the data requested is mainly *statistics*, which should also be publicly available to the administration and publishable.

Three topics that only returned to LDA were government communication and information management, healthcare system and vaccination procurement, COVID-19 reports, vaccination contracts, and legal framework. Since two of the clusters are related to government purchasing, this area should also be represented in the analysis with BERTopic. However, when looking at sample documents on topic #-1 in BERTopic, it appeared that this is where the more general topics related to citizens’ interest in the work of the BMG, as well as on procurement and contracts, landed during the analysis. Since this topic is considered a mix of all documents BERTopic cannot assign, this cluster can and will not be used for this analysis. Nonetheless, this shows that the study could show gaps due to this big cluster of miscellaneous topics that BERTopic grouped. Topics such as cannabis regulation and media advertising only returned in BERTopic as clusters. While the word cannabis returned in the second LDA analysis, the word was mixed with other

Figure 5: Distinct and common topics identified by LDA and BERTopic

more COVID-19-relevant words in a cluster and became, therefore, less relevant as a stand-alone topic.

5 DISCUSSION

This study has shown that a dataset of FOI requests can give information for the user-driven open data ecosystem. The analysis has proven that there are clear indicators of priorities in citizens’ interest in topics. Since the dataset included a period in which citizens were mostly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, the return of mostly, or in the case of the LDA analysis, all topics being COVID-19 related, comes unsurprisingly. During the study, it became clear that the clusters returned in BERTopic were more distinct than in LDA, where some of the returned words appeared in more than one cluster. However, while at first sight, both data analysis methods seemed to return diverging results when looking at the cluster titles, there are some similarities in the topics returned. Both methods returned topics related to vaccination, emergency health care capacity, coronavirus tests, and data protection. The latter could be related to concerns about the app developed during COVID-19, a communication tool to receive test results and save proof of vaccination.

This exercise also showed some obstacles in the data collection and analysis. For instance, the data collection was cumbersome

since it had to be requested at the Ministry of Health, and it took time and effort to get the dataset in the correct format and prepare it for further analysis. Both methods have returned interesting topic clusters, but only BERTopic creates meaning with distinct topics. However, BERTopic’s detriment is the large number of topics categorized as miscellaneous. Here, the authors would have wished for a method to teach BERTopic how to classify and sort those documents better, maybe under the other created topic clusters. The authors believe that LDA would be a great tool to analyze buzzwords related to FOIA requests, where context does not play a role, to understand better what categories of documents citizens would like to see. However, this study has also shown that there is not yet one way to automate the analysis of the dataset perfectly in the context of the user-driven open data ecosystem. Further testing with other datasets would be needed, focusing on the BERTopic to determine whether the large volume of topics categorized as miscellaneous is just a phenomenon in this research or a general issue with BERTopic. This might lead to further development of this instrument to minimize the volume of topics categorized under miscellaneous.

6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This research has generated a couple of recommendations. The pandemic and citizens' reactions to current events influenced the requests and this dataset. Here, it would be interesting to compare the results of this research with a dataset of FOI requests made to another authority that did not deal with health-related issues or select another time period to rule out the pandemic's influence on the results. The methodologies have both proven advantages and disadvantages. Together, they confirmed some main thematic areas that citizens were interested in, confirming that a mixed-method approach seems most advantageous at this research stage. The proposed methodology can be used as a foundation for researchers to adapt to their work and for practitioners to be included either in their policy-making processes or the decision on what datasets should be published with the most urgency. Another thematic area in which this methodology could be applied is financial transparency.

The analysis of this dataset has proven that citizens are interested in information on health-related procurement. Generally, the requests either show a gap in the data publication, an urgency to publish those datasets and change policies accordingly, or an indication that the dataset was not easily accessible. All those factors give public administration and practitioners important pointers on where to focus their open data efforts. While this methodology could be applied to other areas of the government data landscape, additional case studies would enrich research on user-driven open data ecosystems. Applying this approach would help foster the development of a user-driven open data ecosystem. Under the supplier-driven strategy, open data portals often function as one-way street that do not fully align with user demands. This approach would help to create a more balanced and responsive open data system. Secondly, creating a taxonomy of FOI-related words such as information categories and the relation to data formats (e.g., statistics = xls) would be helpful to define not only the information needs and publication priorities but also the formats in which information should be published.

For future research, it is recommended to use already existing FOI portals⁴ and their APIs to download and use the dataset. The authors had to request the dataset from the Ministry of Health since it had yet to be published. However, the pre-processing time could be significantly shortened if the data had been available openly and in a more practicable format. The methodologies also had both their advantages and challenges. In this context, BERTopic was better suited for analyzing the dataset since the eight topics returned in BERTopic cover separate areas and give a more detailed idea of what topics citizens would like to see published by government administration. This is exemplified by the two topics returned in BERTopic that were not found prominently or at all in LDA, which were cannabis legalization, tobacco legislation, and media advertising expenditures. Those two topics would have been lost if the analysis had only been done using LDA.

⁴This could be the portal 'Frag den Staat' in Germany (www.fragdenstaat.de) or 'What do they Know' in the UK (<https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/>) and many more. Most of them operating on the open-source solution Alaveteli <http://alaveteli.org/>.

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